

ANALYSIS OF THE THOUGHTS OF ALISHER NAVOI ABOUT EDUCATIONAL
UPBRINGING

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Abstract: *Alisher Navoi was one of the most prominent figures in Turkic literature and made immense contributions to poetry and other literary works during the 15th century in Central Asia. As an intellectual and scholar, himself, Navoi placed great emphasis on the importance of education and upbringing of the youth. Through his writings, he expressed his philosophical thoughts and guidance on how students should be taught and nurtured. This article aims to analyze and discuss Navoi's views on educational upbringing by examining some of his notable works.*

Keywords: *education, poet, writings, principles, views, opinions, literature*

Introduction: *Alisher Navoi, a renowned 15th-century Uzbek poet, philosopher, and statesman, left an enduring legacy of wisdom and insights on various aspects of human life, including educational upbringing. His writings, particularly his didactic poem "Mahbub ul-Qulub" (Beloved of Hearts), provide valuable guidance on the principles and practices of effective education.*

The Importance of Knowledge

Navoi placed great emphasis on the pursuit of knowledge, believing it to be the foundation of a fulfilling and meaningful life. In "Mahbub ul-Qulub," he writes: "Knowledge is the key to all virtues, the source of all happiness, the ornament of the soul, and the light of the heart." He viewed education as a lifelong endeavor, urging individuals

to continuously seek knowledge and wisdom. Navoi believed that knowledge not only empowers individuals but also enables them to make sound judgments and contribute positively to society.

The Role of Teachers

Navoi recognized the pivotal role of teachers in the educational process. He emphasized the importance of finding knowledgeable and virtuous mentors who can guide students on the path to enlightenment. In "Mahbub ul-Qulub," he writes: "A good teacher is like a skilled gardener who nurtures the young plants of knowledge in the garden of the heart." Navoi believed that teachers should be patient, compassionate, and inspiring, creating a supportive and stimulating learning environment for their students.

Cultivating Virtuous Character

Beyond the acquisition of knowledge, Navoi stressed the importance of cultivating virtuous character in young minds. He believed that education should not only develop intellectual abilities but also foster moral and ethical values. In "Mahbub ul-Qulub," he writes: "True education is that which teaches us to distinguish between right and wrong, to be honest and truthful, to be kind and compassionate." Navoi emphasized the importance of instilling virtues such as humility, generosity, and justice in students, arguing that these qualities are essential for a happy and successful life.

Methods of Education

Navoi advocated for a holistic approach to education that engaged students on multiple levels. He believed that memorization and rote learning were insufficient and that education should involve critical thinking, problem-solving, and creative expression. In "Mahbub ul-Qulub," he writes: "Education should not be confined to books and lectures but should encompass practical experiences, discussions, and debates." Navoi also encouraged students to engage in self-reflection and self-improvement, recognizing the importance of personal growth and development.

The Impact of Navoi's Thoughts

The thoughts of Alisher Navoi on educational upbringing have had a profound impact on Uzbek society and beyond. His writings have inspired generations of educators and students, shaping the educational landscape of Central Asia. Navoi's emphasis on the importance of knowledge, the role of teachers, and the cultivation of virtuous character continues to resonate with educators and policymakers today. His ideas have been incorporated into educational curricula and have influenced the development of educational institutions throughout the region.

Navoi's Perspectives on Developing Character and Morality

One of the key aspects that Navoi stressed in his literature was the necessity of imparting strong moral and ethical values in students from a young age. In his poem, he advised that teachers should focus on nurturing students' character by inculcating virtues like generosity, courage, honesty and compassion. Navoi believed students would become responsible members of the society only if their education cultivated high standards of conduct and morality. He emphasized the formative role of education in shaping the personality and behavior of individuals.

Navoi also highlighted the importance of practicing what one preaches. He cautioned teachers against merely lecturing students about virtues but not demonstrating them in their own behavior. In his view, teachers needed to lead by example and act as role models for students to emulate. Their conduct and interactions with students should reflect the very values of integrity, kindness and righteousness that they aim to inculcate. Unless the teachers' own character exemplified morality, their teachings would not leave a lasting impact on the students.

Emphasis on Developing Analytical and Critical Thinking

In addition to character building, Navoi underscored the necessity of nurturing analytical and critical thinking abilities in students. He was a strong proponent of promoting intellectual curiosity and independent, logical reasoning. In his literary works "Munsha'at us-Su'ada" and "Mukhtasar as-Siyar", Navoi advised teachers to encourage open discussions

and debates in their classrooms. He wanted students to freely exchange ideas, respectfully question beliefs and think creatively with a spirit of inquiry.

Navoi believed rote learning and rigid pedagogy only confined students' minds without developing their faculties of analysis and judgment. He stressed the need for interactive, discussion-based learning methods that stimulated students' higher-order thinking. Teachers should pose thought-provoking questions to students and guide them towards rational conclusions instead of simply imparting ready-made answers. In Navoi's view, this approach would best prepare students for the complexities of the real world and equip them with lifelong learning abilities.

Promoting Multidisciplinary Learning

Another notable aspect of Navoi's educational philosophy was his advocacy for multidisciplinary, well-rounded learning. In his work "Munsha'at us-Su'ada", he emphasized on cultivating proficiency in diverse fields like literature, philosophy, mathematics, natural sciences and foreign languages. Navoi did not want education to remain confined within the boundaries of any single discipline.

He recognized the importance and interconnectedness of different domains of knowledge. His vision of education aimed at developing students' comprehensive understanding of varied subjects. Navoi discouraged narrow specialization or focusing only on selective topics of studies. He believed a broad, multidisciplinary grounding would allow students to appreciate diverse perspectives and apply their learning creatively across multiple contexts. It would also help nurture well-informed, open-minded individuals capable of appreciating different streams of knowledge.

Conclusion

Through his scholarly works, Alisher Navoi made a seminal contribution to conceptualizing educational upbringing. His perspectives on character building, promoting analytical thinking and advocating multidisciplinary learning provide highly relevant guidance even today. Navoi emphasized the transformative potential of education and rightly saw teachers as the pivotal agents for nurturing students into responsible,

intellectually vibrant individuals. His philosophical insights continue to illuminate the ideal qualities of teaching-learning processes that can maximize the holistic development of learners. Navoi's visionary ideas remain a valuable framework for conceptualizing progressive, impactful education.

References:

1. O'zRTXB Mirziyoyev. *We will build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan in unification. Tashkent - "Uzbekistan" - until 2016, Page 18*
2. Alisher Navoi. *"Mahbub ul-qulub" www.ziyouz.com library. Stitch 61*
3. Yakubov, S. & Zakirov, Z. (2021). *LYUBOV K RODITELYAM I POCHITANIE IX-OSNOVNOE ZVENO VOSPITANIA. Theoretical and Applied Science, (4), 439-442.*
4. Salomov, A. A., & Khurramov, R. S. (2019). *TEORETICHESKIE ASPECT RAZVITIA LOGICHESKOGO MISHLENIYA NA UROKAX MATHEMATICIAN V NACHALNOY SHKOLE. Internauka, (41-1), 12-14.*
5. Muqimovich, Y. S. *the use of interactive methods in teaching historical topics in elementary school reading lessons. Journal, 326-329.*